

SIMPILFYING LINGUISTIC COMPLEXITY, CULTURE AND COGNITION IN LANGUAGE EVOLUTION

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Abstract. Language is a social phenomenon that arises as a result of the need for people to interact and exchange ideas. After the emergence of language (which, scientists believe, took place during the primitive community system), society began to develop rapidly. This article discusses in detail Simplifying linguistic complexity, culture and cognition in language evolution.

Keywords: language complexity, coherence and cognition, language evolution, society, grammatical construction and etc.

Language serves the society, the people who are its members, so language is a social phenomenon, that is, the language belongs not to the individual, but to the whole society, and is formed and developed with the help of the members of this society. Due to this, the fate of language is closely linked with the fate of society. Without language, there can be no society, that is, language is a great blessing that unites people as a society. There can be no language without society. Members of the community also contribute to the survival and development of the language. In this regard, it is worth recalling the state of the Uzbek language in the 80s and 90s of the last century. During this period, the scope of the Uzbek language became much narrower and it was in danger of extinction. It is a complex phenomenon in terms of language structure, which consists of the following interconnected parts:

1. The system of sounds.
2. Vocabulary or vocabulary.
3. Grammatical construction.

As you know, human language is a sound language. Each language has its own sound system. Sounds form words, phrases, grammatical forms and indicators. The set of words and phrases consisting of sounds is the vocabulary of the language. Vocabulary-rich words and phrases serve as a building block for the sentence. Speech, the rules of its construction are determined by the grammatical structure of the language. Thus, the system of sounds, vocabulary, grammatical structure, which are the components of the language, are closely interrelated and require the existence of one another. Each concrete language with its members forms a whole system, system, language system.

Language exhibits striking systematic structure. Words are composed of combinations of reusable sounds, and those words in turn are combined to form complex sentences. These properties make language unique among natural communication systems and enable our species to convey an open-ended set of messages. We provide a cultural evolutionary account of the origins of this structure. We show, using simulations of rational learners and laboratory experiments, that structure arises from a trade-off between pressures for compressibility (imposed during learning) and expressivity (imposed during communication). We further demonstrate that the relative strength of these two pressures can be varied in different social contexts, leading to novel predictions about the emergence of structured behaviour in the wild. Understanding the origins of this structure is a central goal of cognitive science. A recent productive approach treats it as a consequence of cultural evolution. Languages, in common with many other human behaviours, persist through a repeated cycle of learning and production: individuals learn a language by observing the linguistic behaviour of their speech community, and the linguistic behaviour they subsequently produce shapes learning in others. Languages potentially change and evolve as a result of their transmission, adapting to the biases inherent in the processes of language learning and language use.

The fact that language is compositional and combinatorial – that it has system-wide structure – also means that languages as whole systems are compressible, i.e., allow the formation of compressed representations. We commonly refer to these representations as grammars, which are concise descriptions of the generative system underlying a language. These are compressed to the degree that they are more concise than a simple listing of all the possible utterances in a language. Note that this notion of compressibility is orthogonal to the compressibility of signals themselves.² For example, regular morphological paradigms are highly systematic and therefore highly compressible, but this potentially comes at the cost of less efficient signals, since exploiting unsystematic irregulars might allow shorter forms. Linguists are, of course, interested in some objective assessment of complexity. In general, it would be nice to find out whether there are actually more simple or more complex languages regardless of how they are written and who learns them. Thus, let's say if a Martian came to our planet and would have to learn some different languages in their oral form, as it is the primary form of language, whether it would be more difficult for him to learn Finnish or Serbian or Chinese or Hindi. That's the question, in fact, that the linguistic study of linguistic complexity tries to answer.

This area of science is relatively young, and it actually began to develop actively only in the last 20-25 years. Before that, linguists held as an axiom the notion that all

languages are of equal complexity. It was in some ways helpful because it allowed linguists not to extol some languages over others, that is, not to make value judgments. Nevertheless, when all the linguistic community has finally understood and realized that all the 6,000-7,000 languages that exist on our planet are equivalent as objects of study, we were able to set ourselves this question: "So what languages are more or less complex?" How to measure linguistic complexity, it is not at all obvious and not completely understood. Here, linguistics uses ideas that come from information theory. Russian mathematician Andrei Kolmogorov introduced a formal definition of complexity, which is now called "the Kolmogorov complexity". The complexity of an object is the length of the most economical descriptions of the object in some formalized description language. I am, of course, simplifying it, without going into the mathematical details of the wording, but that's the way it works. There are no such clearly formalized description languages which would be applicable to all of the world's languages so we have to look for some correlates of language complexity that can be measured in order to calculate what languages are more complex, and what languages are simpler.

How language and cognition interact in thinking? Is language just used for communication of completed thoughts, or is it fundamental for thinking? Existing approaches have not led to a computational theory. We develop a hypothesis that language and cognition are two separate but closely interacting mechanisms. Language accumulates cultural wisdom; cognition develops mental representations modeling surrounding world and adapts cultural knowledge to concrete circumstances of life. Language is acquired from surrounding language "ready-made" and therefore can be acquired early in life. This early acquisition of language in childhood encompasses the entire hierarchy from sounds to words, to phrases, and to highest concepts existing in culture. Cognition is developed from experience. Yet cognition cannot be acquired from experience alone; language is a necessary intermediary, a "teacher."

It has been seen that language is much more than the external expression and communication of internal thoughts formulated independently of their verbalization. In demonstrating the inadequacy and inappropriateness of such a view of language, attention has already been drawn to the ways in which one's native language is intimately and in all sorts of details related to the rest of one's life in a community and to smaller groups within that community. This is true of all peoples and all languages; it is a universal fact about language. Anthropologists speak of the relations between language and culture. It is indeed more in accordance with reality to consider language as a part of culture. Culture is here being used, as it is throughout this article, in the anthropological sense, to refer to all aspects of human life insofar as they are

determined or conditioned by membership in a society. The fact that people eat or drink is not in itself cultural; it is a biological necessity for the preservation of life.

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